

Shifting Work Landscapes: An Analysis of Post-Pandemic Work From Home Patterns in the UK

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Summary

The COVID-19 crisis instigated significant societal transformations, some with lasting impacts. Social distancing emerged as a crucial method for infection control, leading to government advocacy for work from home (WFH) practices. Post-pandemic, a shift from mandatory to voluntary WFH, including location-flexible working, was observed. This study assesses the evolution of WFH patterns in the UK, focusing on hybrid models, pre- and post-pandemic. Utilizing GPS data from February over three years (2019-2021), it identified residential and workplace locations, employing time and distance metrics to ascertain WFH. The research analysed geographical trends in WFH domiciles and workplaces across this period, exploring the dynamics and determinants of these shifts.

KEYWORDS: working from home, the Covid-19, GPS data, spatial and temporal analysis

1. Introduction

Pandemic has provided a captivating experiment. The pre-COVID-19 world was a so-called "business-as-usual" model. The governments' promotion of curtailing human mobility not only mitigates the peril of contagion, but also promotes WFH. In this case, there has been the largest "work from home" switch ever. The pandemic has forced organisations around the world to quickly get on the fast track to the future of work and adapt to a new remote reality.

Currently, most studies on WFH are based on research analysis of questionnaire and interview information and further modelling (Pratt, J. H., 1984; Šmite, Darja, et al., 2023). Few studies used mobile phone location data as a dataset to analyse and study WFH based on a spatio-temporal perspective. Moreover, generally studies on WFH were limited to a few fixed fields, such as management and sociology. In terms of GPS data processing, these researches generally stops at getting the meaning of the point or getting a better method, but there are fewer studies that further incorporate socio-demographic information (Huang, L., Li, Q. and Yue, Y., 2010; Farkas, I. et al., 2021). There are relatively few analytical studies at multiple geographical scales in the UK on exploring spatial and temporal changes in WFH under the influence of the COVID-19.

Therefore, this project studied a comparison of users' residential and workplace mobility patterns at multiple scales. Using a GPS dataset rather than a traditional questionnaire dataset explores and compares the patterns of WFH and their influencing factors. The research process is organised into 3 parts: processing and analysing data, making rules, and correlation analysis. Combining the actual situation, rules defining WFH workers were developed based on GPS data. Based on the results of the rules, the changes of WFH before and during the epidemic were compared. The correlation between WFH workers and Demographic data was also explored through Pearson analysis.

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2. Rules for WFH workers based on GPS data

2.1. GPS Dataset

The Mobile App GPS data used were extracted by processing raw trajectory data for homes and workplaces in Middle level geographies. For privacy reasons, the raw data did not contain social information about the user. Generation of these meaningful points required firstly the stay points within the spatial extent within 100 metres in diameter and stay time more than 5 minutes during a day and from these stay points were extracted the points with time constraints during the daytime (9 am to 6 pm) and nighttime (9 pm to 7 am).

2.2. Rules for WFH workers

Regarding rule formulation, as Pan, Yixuan, et al. (2023) mentioned that time limit is the most effective way to identify meaningful points, so time limit is used to formulate rules. Given that it is difficult to distinguish between a full-time WFH worker and a non-worker, the rule was developed to be orientated towards hybrid workers. This study was limited to those who were likely to WFH. Hybrid work is a combination of two office modes, in-office and teleworking, i.e. working from home for part of the week.

For the identification rule, the home location is the place that stays at night for the longest time. Locations where the user stayed more than 4 hours during the daytime are considered as workplace alternatives. This requires a user to have at least two workplace alternatives. The user needs to meet two conditions. One condition is that the distance between the user's home and one or more of the workplace alternatives is less than or equal to 100 meters, i.e., it may also be the location of the user's home. The other is that the distance between home and one or more of the workplace alternatives is greater than 100 meters. In this case, the user is considered to be a WFH worker.

Figure 1. Two conditions for WFH workers

3. Analysis

Spatial and temporal analyses of WFH were analysed using GPS data February over three years. Further reflection on the selection of correlation study factors through changes.

3.1. Demographic Data

The UK was used as a study area. Regions, middle level geographies and Local Authority District (LAD) were taken as the regional division (Table 1). February 2019, February 2020 and February 2021 were chosen for the study.

Table 1 The geographic level description to the dataset.

Geographic level	Description
Area	England, Wales, Scotland and North Ireland
Middle level geographies	Middle Layer Super Output Area (MSOA) in England and Wales Intermediate Zone in Scotland and District Electoral Area in North Ireland
Local Authority District (LAD)	England, Wales, Scotland and North Ireland

Depending on the data, different demographic data are used at different geographic levels (**Table 2**). These variables were selected by references and similar statistical reports.

Table 2 The geographic level corresponds to the demographic data.

Geographic level	Demographic data
Middle level Geographies	The deprivation indices of income
Middle level Geographies	The deprivation indices of employment
Middle level Geographies	Population density
LAD	Population density
LAD	Age
LAD	Gender

3.2. Correlation Analysis

Correlations between these indicators and household and workplace were tested using the the deprivation indices of income and employment and the population density composite. Correlation analyses were made to cross-reference WFH data with census data. The correlations were calculated using the Pearson index.

4. Result

Key findings indicate the most pronounced changes in 2020. A trend towards sparser populated areas was noted during the pandemic. The distribution of WFH individuals mirrored the general sample, with an observable trend of these individuals being positioned further from their homes and workplaces over time. Correlation analysis showed a higher propensity for WFH among those aged 15-39, with more women than men engaging in WFH. These observations concur with the Office for National Statistics reports. Additionally, a slight inverse correlation was found between the prevalence of homeworking and regional indices of income and employment deprivation.

The project found that WFH users' homes and workplaces changed most significantly in 2020 compared to before the pandemic. During the pandemic, there was a tendency for homes and workplaces to move towards areas of low population density. WFH users' homes were more likely to become farther away from their workplaces over time.

As for WFH workers, at the middle level geographies, a certain positive correlation between the number of users and the population density. There was a weak negative correlation between the distribution of homeworkers and regional income and employment deprivation indices. The negative correlation was most pronounced in 2020, suggesting that in 2020 WFH workers were more likely to be distributed in areas with low deprivation indices.

In LAD level, Population density showed a negative correlation with the number of worker in the unit during the pandemic, but a positive correlation before the pandemic. About age groups, Individuals aged between 15 and 39 were more likely to WFH, while those over 65 years age were the least likely.

As for gender, the results shows that there may be more women among WFH workers, which is in line with the ONS report (Office for National Statistics, 2022). Overall, the results of the correlation are similar to the data reported by the UK government (Office for National Statistics, 2022).

Figure 2. WFH Correlation Matrix Heatmap in LAD Level in 2020

5. Conclusion

The phenomenon of people moving towards areas with low population density and longer distances between home and workplace is consistent with that described by the following two hypotheses. The first one is the hypothesis that showed WFH workers may be more tolerant of long commutes (NILLES, J. M., 1991). The 'Doughnut Effect' by Ramani, A. & Bloom, N. (2021) explained the shift of homes and businesses from densely populated central districts to less dense suburban.

As for women possibly choosing to WFH, Lyttelton, T. et al. (2022) illustrated that women preferred to WFH so that they can reconcile family and childcare. Young people were less likely to WFH than other age groups, due to the fact that these workers needed more opportunities for promotion and socialisation (Pratt, J. H., 1984; Cappelli, P., 2021). The correlation was most clearly demonstrated in 2020, probably because in 2020 the Covid-19 was widespread in the UK and the government implemented lockdown policy.

Overall, this study used non-traditional data to study WFH from a new perspective and further combined the results with demographic data and the final results partially matched the statistical report. Further research work could consider expanding the scope of comparative analyses in time or space.

References

- Baruch, Y. (2000) Teleworking: benefits and pitfalls as perceived by professionals and managers. *New technology, work, and employment*. 15 (1), 34 - 49.
- Cappelli, P. (2021) *The Future of the Office: Work from Home, Remote Work, and the Hard Choices We All Face*. Philadelphia: Wharton School Press.
- Farkas, I. et al. (2021) 'Dynamic Identification of Stop Locations from GPS Trajectories Based on Their Temporal and Spatial Characteristics', in *Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning - ICANN 2021*. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing AG. pp. 347 -
- Huang, L., Li, Q., & Yue, Y. (2010). Activity identification from GPS trajectories using spatial

temporal POIs' attractiveness. Workshop on Location-based Social Networks.

Lyttelton, T. et al. (2022) Telecommuting and gender inequalities in parents' paid and unpaid work before and during the COVID - 19 pandemic. *Journal of marriage and family*. 84 (1), 230 - 249.

NILLES, J. M. (1991) Telecommuting and urban sprawl : mitigator or inciter? *Transportation (Dordrecht)*. 18 (4), 411 - 432.

Office for National Statistics (2022). ' Is hybrid working here to stay? '. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/employmentandemployeetypes/articles/ishybridworkingheretostay/2022-05-23> (Accessed: 21 August 2023).

Pan, Y. et al. (2023) Residency and worker status identification based on mobile device location data. *Transportation research. Part C, Emerging technologies*. 146, 103956–.

Pratt, J. H. (1984) Home teleworking: A study of its pioneers. *Technological forecasting & social change*. 25 (1), 1–14.

Šmite, Darja, et al. (2023) From Forced Working-From-Home to Voluntary Working-from-Anywhere: Two Revolutions in Telework. *The Journal of Systems and Software*, 195, pp. 111509–111509,

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